

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Subplot treatments were grades of Zn-DAP (1-6%) applied before transplanting; ZnSO₄ soil application (25 kg/ha); ZnSO₄ foliar application (0.5% sprayed 30 and 45 d after transplanting); seedling roots dipped in 2% ZnO suspension; and no Zn (control). Main plots were with and without green manure at 12.5 t/ha (sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea* L. in wet season and pongam leaves *Pongamia glabra* Vent. in summer). All plots received 100-21.9-41.5 kg NPK/ha.

Zn application significantly increased grain yield (see table); 6% Zn-DAP was both efficient and economical. □

Effect of Zn-DAP on grain yield of rainfed lowland rice.

Treatment	1985 wet season yield (t/ha)		1986 summer yield (t/ha)		Zn added (kg/ha)
	With GM	No GM	With GM	No GM	
No Zn-SSP	5.2	5.1	5.3	5.1	—
1% Zn-DAP	5.9	5.7	5.7	5.6	1.1
2% Zn-DAP	6.0	5.8	6.4	5.5	2.2
3% Zn-DAP	6.1	5.9	6.7	6.0	3.4
4% Zn-DAP	6.2	5.9	6.6	5.7	4.6
5% Zn-DAP	6.2	5.9	6.8	6.2	5.8
6% Zn-DAP	6.4	6.0	6.7	6.5	7.1
ZnSO ₄ - basal	6.1	5.7	6.5	5.7	5.8
ZnSO ₄ - foliar	5.9	5.7	6.1	5.9	—
ZnO root dip	6.2	5.4	6.2	5.6	—
No Zn-DAP	—	—	5.6	5.1	—
LSD (0.05)					
Green manure (GM)		ns		ns	
Zn treatments		0.5		0.6	
GM × Zn		ns		ns	
Zn × GM		ns		ns	

Efficiency of prilled urea (PU) and urea supergranules (USG) in rapidly percolating soil

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We studied the fate and efficiency of PU and USG in rice grown on a rapidly percolating loamy sand at PAU farm. Soil was a Typic Ustochrept, CEC 4.5 meq/100 g, pH 8.2, 0.3% organic C, 0.06% total N, with an N mineralization rate of 16 mg N/kg soil after 7 d anaerobic incubation at 40 °C.

N was applied at 0, 37.5, 75.0, and 112.5 kg N/ha in plots measuring 4.8 × 4.8 m. In the plots with 75.0 kg N/ha, ¹⁵N-labeled PU and USG with 5 atom percent excess ¹⁵N were applied in rectangular metal frame microplots (1.2 × 0.8 × 0.3 m) within the main plots. PU was applied in 3 equal splits at transplanting, active tillering, and panicle initiation; USG was placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 rice hills in alternate rows. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Rice variety PR106 was transplanted the last week of Jun, 35 d after seeding, and harvested the last week of Oct. Grain and straw samples were analyzed

Effect of N source and level on growth, yield, and N uptake of rice.

Treatment	Plant ht (m)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Yield (t/ha)		N uptake (kg/ha)		Apparent recovery (%)
			Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	
Control	84	232	3.7	4.5	36	11	—
PU 37.5	89	297	5.0	6.0	49	18	55
PU 75.0	96	308	5.7	7.3	57	25	48
PU 112.5	101	391	7.0	7.4	77	24	48
USG 37.5	82	255	3.7	4.1	37	12	4
USG 75.0	94	285	4.4	5.5	43	14	14
USG 112.5	91	267	4.8	4.7	45	13	10
LSD (0.05)	7	33	0.7	2.1	9	7	—

Balance of ¹⁵N-labeled fertilizer in rice.

for total N content and N uptake. Soil was destructively sampled at harvest with a rectangular soil sampler (30 × 13.3 × 50 cm) for total Kjeldahl N and ¹⁵N analyses.

Plant height, number of panicles, yield, and N uptake showed that PU was significantly superior to USG (see table). Apparent recovery of N was higher with PU (48-55%) than with

USG (4-14%). Labeled N utilization was 42% with PU, 30% in grain and 12% in straw (see figure). Only 8% of the labeled N applied as USG was utilized (6% in grain and 2% in straw).

Isotopic composition of rice grain and straw showed that 40% grain N and 35%

straw N were derived from PU; 13% grain N and 12% straw N were derived from USG.

Soil analysis at harvest showed that 26% of the labeled N from PU and 13% from USG were retained in the soil. Total recovery of labeled N in crop and

soil was 68% for PU, 21% for USG; 32% PU N and 79% USG N was not accounted for in the N balance. The large deficit of N from USG was attributed to its rapid movement and leaching from concentrated zones at placement sites. □

Sesbania rostrata — a lower-cost source of N for rice

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We studied the effect of stem-root nodulating *S. rostrata* and sunn hemp *Crotalaria jancea* on transplanted irrigated rice Mandya Vijaya (145-150 d duration) during summer 1988.

Soil of the experimental site was red sandy loam (Alfisols), pH 6.3, medium N (1.1% organic matter), 10.6 kg available Olsen's P/ha, and 151 kg available K/ha. N content was 4.1% in *S. rostrata* and 3.2% in sunn hemp.

At the same level of applied N, yield increased significantly (15%) over farmers' practice (treatment 1), with 30% N supplied through *S. rostrata* (treatment 2) (see table). The cost

involved in supplying N through *S. rostrata* was \$12, compared to urea cost of \$15. Use of *S. rostrata* increased net profit by \$125/ha. *S. rostrata* (treatment 4) could substitute for fertilizer N up to 70 kg N/ha (treatment 6) without significant yield reduction.

S. rostrata was significantly superior to sunn hemp (treatment 5). Uptake of N was better with *S. rostrata*. □

Effect of *S. rostrata* on rice yield. ^a Karnataka, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Total uptake of N in grain + straw (kg/ha)
1. 100 kg N/ha as urea in 3 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/4 at tillering + 1/4 panicle initiation (farmers' practice)	4.5	92
2. 30 kg N/ha through <i>S. rostrata</i> + 70 kg N/ha as urea in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	5.2	110
3. 30 kg N/ha through sunn hemp <i>C. jancea</i> + 70 kg N/ha in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	4.8	97
4. <i>S. rostrata</i> to supply 70 kg N/ha	3.4	76
5. Sunn hemp to supply 70 kg N/ha	3.0	68
6. 70 kg N/ha as urea in 2 splits: 1/2 at planting + 1/2 at tillering	3.2	71
7. Control (no N)	2.4	47
LSD (0.05)	0.3	6
CV (%)	10.8	5.3

^aAll treatments received 22 kg P and 41 kg K/ha.

Nitrogen-use efficiency with hand- and machine-applied N fertilizers in wetland rice soils

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Prilled urea (PU) farmer's split (F), researcher's split (R), modified split (M), applicator placed (AP); and urea

supergranules (USG) hand placed (H) and AP were compared in a field experiment during the 1986 dry season. BR3 was the test variety.

Soil was clay loam (Paleudults) with pH 6.5, 1.05% organic matter, CEC 24 meq/100 g, 0.07% total N, and incubated 57 ppm NH₄⁺-N (incubated at 30 °C for 1 wk). Two rates of N (58 and 87 kg/ha) and 1 control treatment were used. P at 17.6 kg/ha, K at 33.2 kg/ha, and S at 20 kg/ha were applied

Effect of N fertilizer application method on yield of BR3 and agronomic efficiency of N, 1986 dry season, BRRI, Joydebpur, Bangladesh. ^a

Treatment ^a	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./m ²)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Agronomic efficiency (kg grain/kg N)
Control	86	210 e	195 c	3.6 c	-
58 PU (F)	93	243 d	231 b	4.9 ab	23
58 PU (R)	91	286 bc	269 ab	4.6 b	18
58 PU (M)	89	267 bcd	256 ab	4.8 ab	20
58 PU (AP)	94	309 a	295 a	5.3 a	30
58 USG (H)	93	299 a	283 a	5.3 ab	29
58 USG (AP)	94	285 abc	269 ab	5.4 a	31
87 PU (F)	91	272 abcd	263 ab	5.2 ab	19
87 PU (R)	92	260 cd	242 b	5.0 ab	16
87 PU (M)	94	281 abcd	268 ab	4.9 ab	15
87 USG (H)	94	293 ab	271 ab	5.4 a	20
CV (%)	4	2	2	8	

^a Within a column, means followed by a common letter do not vary significantly at the 5% level of DMRT. ^b F = 1/3 basal + 1/3 30 d after transplanting (DT) + 1/3 at panicle initiation (PI), R = 2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI, M = 1/3 15 DT + 30 DT + 1/3 at PI, AP = applicator-placed at 10-12 cm depth, H = hand-placed at about 10-12 cm depth.